

Composition of less Familiar Metal Cyanogen Complexes: Part I. Composition of Cu(i) and Cr(ii) Cobalticyanide by Electrometric Methods

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Crystalline potassium cyanocobaltate(III) was prepared by Pichler's method and cuprous chloride by Groger's method. The composition of the precipitate formed by their interaction was determined employing potentiometric and amperometric techniques. Chromous chloride was prepared by Balltis and Bailor's method and its interaction with potassium cobalticyanide was similarly studied.

Chemical literature abounds in references on the properties and composition of metal complexes of alkali ferro and ferricyanides. But very little attention appears to have been paid to the study of metal complexes of potassium cobalto and cobalticyanides. The worthmentioning references are of Watt and Thompson who carried out the reduction of potassium hexacyanocobaltate(III) to potassium tetracyanocobaltate(I) with potassium in presence of liquid ammonia. On reviewing the literature it has been found that no attempt has yet been made to study the composition of the precipitates obtained by the interaction of potassium cobalticyanide with metal ions. This communication deals with the results on the composition of the precipitates obtained by the interaction of Cu(I) and Cr(II) with potassium hexacyanocobaltate(III) using physico-chemical methods.

EXPERIMENTAL

Potassium hexacyanocobaltate (III): Crystals of potassium hexacyanocobaltate(III) were prepared by the method of Zwenger² and later on modified by Benedetti Pichler³. Cobalt cyanide was precipitated from a vigorously stirred boiling solution of cobalt chloride (4 gms. of $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in 500 ml of water) by dropwise addition of potassium cyanide solution (30 gms. of KCN dissolved in 200 ml of water). The reddish brown precipitate of cobalt cyanide was removed by filtration, washed with cold water, and while still moist transferred to a beaker containing 60 gms. of KCN dissolved in 200 ml of water. The mixture was stirred until the precipitate dissolved. The deep red potassium hexacyanocobaltate(II) solution thus obtained changed to yellow potassium hexacyanocobaltate (III) on boiling for 10—15 minutes. On cooling, yellow crystals of potassium hexacyanocobaltate(III) separated out and it was filtered while hot and washed with

1. G. W. Watt and R. I. T. Thompson, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1959, **9**, 311.
2. Zwenger *Ann.*, 1847, **62**, 163.
3. Benedetti Pichler, *Z. anal. Chem.*, 1927, **70**, 257.
4. Groger: *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1890, **28**, 154.

cold water. The crystals thus obtained were dried in a vacuum desiccator. The weighed amount of the dried crystals was dissolved to prepare a standard solution.

Copper(I) Chloride: Cuprous chloride was prepared by reducing a solution of Cu(II) chloride with copper turnings in presence of hydrochloric acid. The precipitate obtained was filtered by suction and washed with air free solution of sulphurous acid (prepared by passing sulphur dioxide in air free water). Finally, the precipitate was washed with ether and dried in vacuum desiccator. A weighed amount of cuprous chloride was dissolved in air free solution of potassium chloride (2.0 M) and few drops of conc. hydrochloric acid were added so as to make the solution clear. The strength of the solution was determined by titrating it against ammonium sulphocyanide using ferrous ammonium sulphate as indicator.

Chromium(II) Chloride: Chromous chloride crystals were prepared by the method recommended by Balltis and Bailor^{5,6}. These were dissolved in double distilled water and the solution was stored and standardized according to the method used by Lingane and Pecsok⁷.

Titrations: The potentiometric titrations were performed with Pye Precision Vernier Potentiometer (Cat. No. 7568). A platinum wire (1 cm) fused in Pyrex glass tube was used as the indicator electrode and S.C.E. as the reference. The direct as well as the reverse potentiometric titrations between cuprous chloride and potassium cobalticyanide were carried out using equimolar solutions at five different concentrations (0.1M, 0.05M, 0.025M, 0.16M and 0.1M of $K_3Co(CN)_6$ against 0.076M, 0.076M, 0.025M, 0.16M and 0.1M of $CrCl_2$ respectively).

Direct titrations were performed taking potassium hexacyanocobaltate(III) in the cell and the solutions of cuprous chloride and chromous chloride in the burette and vice versa for the reverse titrations. After each addition, solutions were stirred by a current of purified nitrogen, so as to mix the solutions and create an inert atmosphere to check the oxidation of Cu(I) and Cr(II) while carrying out the reverse titrations.

The amperometric titrations were carried out by Fisher Elecdropode (Sensitivity 2x) with a multiflex galvanometer (Type MGF2) in the external circuit. The titrations between cuprous chloride and potassium cobalticyanide were carried out at 0.4 volts whereas those between chromous chloride and potassium cobalticyanide were carried out at 0.05V. The decomposition potentials were determined from the polarograms drawn for cuprous chloride and chromous chloride solutions using 2M potassium chloride as the base electrolyte and 0.05% gelatine as the maximum suppressor. The titrations between cuprous chloride and potassium cobalticyanide were carried out using 1.2 ml, 1.0 ml, 0.8 ml, 0.6 ml and 0.4 ml of 0.005M $K_3Co(CN)_6$ against 0.01M CuCl for direct titrations and 1.2 ml, 1.0 ml, 0.8 ml, 0.6 ml and 0.4 ml of 0.01M CuCl against 0.05 $K_3Co(CN)_6$ for reverse titrations. The titrations between chromous chloride and potassium cobalticyanide were carried out using 2.4 ml, 2.0 ml, 1.6 ml, 1.2 ml, 0.8ml of 0.1M $K_3Co(CN)_6$ against

5. J. H. Balthis Jr. and J. C. Bailar Jr. *J. Amer Chem. Soc.*, 1936, **58**, 1474,

6. F. D. Dutton and H. S. Booth, *Inorganic Synthesis*, Vol. I, 125, 1st. Edition, McGraw Hill Book Company, Inc, New York.

7. J. J. Lingane and R. L. Pecsok, *Anal. Chem.*, 1948, **20**, 425.

0.25M CrCl_2 for direct titrations and 2.4 ml, 2.0 ml, 1.6 ml, 1.2 ml and 0.8 ml of 0.25M CrCl_2 against 0.1M $\text{K}_3\text{Co}(\text{CN})_6$ for reverse titrations.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The typical titration curves are given in figures 1 and 2. The potentiometric as well as amperometric titrations carried out between cuprous chloride and potassium

FIG. 1

- Curve 1 0.005M $\text{K}_3\text{Co}(\text{CN})_6$ in cell & 0.01M CuCl in burette
 Curve 2 0.01M CuCl in cell & 0.005M $\text{K}_3\text{Co}(\text{CN})_6$ in burette
 Curve 3 0.1M $\text{K}_3\text{Co}(\text{CN})_6$ in cell & 0.25M CrCl_2 in burette
 Curve 4 0.25M CrCl_2 in cell & 0.1M $\text{K}_3\text{Co}(\text{CN})_6$ in burette

FIG. 2

- Curve 1 0.01M $\text{K}_3\text{Co}(\text{CN})_6$ in the cell & 0.01M CrCl_2 in burette
 Curve 2 0.01M CuCl in the cell & 0.01M $\text{K}_3\text{Co}(\text{CN})_6$ in burette
 Curve 3 0.025M $\text{K}_3\text{Co}(\text{CN})_6$ in the cell & 0.025M CuCl in burette
 Curve 4 0.01M CrCl_2 in the cell & 0.01M $\text{K}_3\text{Co}(\text{CN})_6$ in burette

